

**The larvae of sawflies and their allies housed in the
Hymenoptera Collection of the Hungarian Natural History Museum
(Hymenoptera: Symphyta)**

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Abstract – A list and collecting data of all larvae belonging to the paraphyletic group Symphyta (sawflies and their allies) (Hymenoptera), housed in the Hymenoptera Collection of the Hungarian National Museum Public Collection Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest, are provided. Specimens identified mostly to species, occasionally only to genus, are stored in 151 vials, presently unidentified material in 73 vials.

Key words – larva collection, collecting data, host plants, unidentified material

INTRODUCTION

Before the active years of the author as a curator (1975–2007) in the Hymenoptera Collection of the Hungarian National Museum Public Collection Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest (HNHM), there was virtually no larval material preserved in the scientific collection. Motivated by a similar material in the Lepidoptera Collection of the HNHM, the author started to collect larvae of Symphyta (a paraphyletic group of Hymenoptera including sawflies and their allies) from 1969 on, and also acquired materials via donations from various colleagues.

The identification of most of the accumulated specimens has remained an overdue debt until now. In the frame of this study, the author identified and/or re-examined and re-evaluated the entire material based primarily on the works of ENSLIN (1918), HERING (1957), LORENZ & KRAUS (1957), ZOMBORI (1982, 2022, 2023, 2025), ALTENHOFER & ZOMBORI (1987), TAEGER & BLANK (2006), and ROLLER & HARIS (2008). During the work the locality labels of the material were revised and, if necessary, completed with missing data, and the vials were arranged according to the systematic order.

The symphytan larva collection of the HNHM is stored in ethanol and preserved in 224 vials at the present. Of them, 151 have been identified by the author to species, or in some cases only to genus level, while 73 have remained unidentified due to various reasons (e.g., lacking or incomplete collecting data, unsatisfactory condition of the specimens, lack of comparative material from the given region, etc.). One vial can contain from a single to several (40+) specimens pertaining to the same species and bearing the same collecting data, and specimens pertaining to a given species and with the same collecting data might be preserved in several vials.

The collection contains a number of faunistically and/or morphologically valuable and interesting specimens representing species such as *Blasticotoma filiceti* Klug, 1834, *Heterarthrus flavicollis* (Gussakovskij, 1947), *Silliana lhommei* (Hering, 1934), *Periclista lineolata* (Klug, 1816), *Harpiphorus lepidus* (Klug, 1818), *Pseudodineura enslini* (Hering, 1923), *Nematus trilineatus* Norton, 1867, or *Syrista parreyssii* (Spinola, 1843). While the majority of the identified material originates from Hungary, the faunas of neighbouring countries, particularly Austria, Romania, and Ukraine, are also well represented, with noteworthy material from the Caucasus and North Korea as well.

The list of the identified symphytan material generally follows the nomenclature and systematic order of TAEGER & BLANK (2006). Within each family-rank taxon, treated species are listed in alphabetical order of their generic and then species names. Names of host plants follow the World Flora Online*. The list of the unidentified symphytan material is ordered by the countries of origin (listed alphabetically), and provides collecting data only, occasionally with remarks. Localities of the labels are given verbatim, with explanatory notes in square brackets if necessary; however, names of countries are always given in English forms here, even if on the original labels they are missing, incomplete, or are indicated in Hungarian or Latinised forms.

LIST OF IDENTIFIED MATERIAL

Blasticotomidae

Blasticotoma filiceti Klug, 1834

Material examined – Ukraine, Kárpátalja [= Zakarpattia Oblast], Máramarosi k. k. term. véd. ter. vendégház [= nature conservation area, guest house], Uglya [= Uglja], 600 m, 28.VII.1998, from stem of *Athyrium* sp. (Athyriaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

* <https://www.worldfloraonline.org> (accessed 20 January 2026)

Argidae*Arge berberidis* Schrank, 1802

Material examined – Hungary, Debrecen, 10.VI.1971, det. L. Zombori.

Remarks – The collector was not recorded; according to Zoltán Varga (University of Debrecen, pers. comm.) the collector might be Zoltán Siroki (University of Debrecen).

Arge ochropus (Gmelin, 1790)

Material examined – USSR Armenia [now Armenia], Yerevan, 1000 m, Bot. Garden [= botanical garden], 25.VII.1977, leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Tiszaigar, Arboretum, 13.IX.1977, from *Rosa* sp. (Rosaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Arge pagana (Panzer, 1797)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovácsi, southern maize fields, 16.VII.1974, netting, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Diprionidae*Neodiprion sertifer* (Geoffroy, 1785)

Material examined – Hungary, Bugac, Ósborókás [= juniper forest], 11.VI.1980, from *Pinus silvestris* L. (Pinaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Pamphiliidae*Acantholyda erythrocephala* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined – Austria, Sollenau, ca. 31.V.1982, leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Neurotoma saltuum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined – Hungary, Debrecen, 7.VII.1965.

Remarks – The collector was not recorded; according to Zoltán Varga (University of Debrecen, pers. comm.) the collector might be Zoltán Siroki (University of Debrecen).

Tenthredinidae: Dolerinae*Dolerus cothurnatus* Lepeletier, 1823

Material examined – Romania, Transsylvania, Bálványos [= Băile Bálványos, Turia], 2.VIII.2009, from *Equisetum* sp. (Equisetaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Dolerus sp.

Material examined – Hungary, Garabonc, 18.IX.1986, from *Equisetum telmateia* Ehrh. (Equisetaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Tenthredinidae: Selandriinae*Strongylogaster mixta* (Klug, 1817)

Material examined – Italy, Genova, Voltri, 3.VI.1979, from *Pteridium aquilinum* (L.) Kuhn (Dennstaedtiaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori; Romania, Transsylvania, Krassó-Szörény m. [= Caraş-Severin County], Szörényi-havasok [= Masivul Severin], Karánsebes [= Caransebeş], Borló [= Borlova], Muntele Mic, 500 m, 15–16.VI.2002, from *Pteridium aquilinum*, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Tenthredinidae: Allantinae*Allantus viennensis* (Schrank, 1781)

Material examined – USSR Armenia [now Armenia], Yerevan, 1000 m, Bot. Garden [= botanical garden], 25.VII.1977, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Ametastegia glabrata (Fallén, 1808)

Material examined – Hungary, Győr, 18.II.1983, prepupa, det. L. Zombori.
Remarks – The collector was not recorded.

Athalia rosae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined – Hungary, Debrecen, 4.IX.1968, det. L. Zombori.

Remarks – The collector was not recorded; according to Zoltán Varga (University of Debrecen, pers. comm.) the collector might be Zoltán Siroki (University of Debrecen).

Eriocampa ovata (Linnaeus, 1761)

Material examined – Austria, Rappottenstein, ca. 23.VII.1987, from *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn. (Betulaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Harpiphorus lepidus (Klug, 1818)

Material examined – Hungary, Újszentmargita, protected forest, 14.IX.1977, from *Quercus robur*, leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Máriagyúd, 1.VI.1978, from *Quercus robur* L. (Fagaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Tenthredinidae: Blennocampinae*Blennocampa pusilla* (Klug, 1816)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 6.VI.1980, leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 27.V.1984, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Cladardis elongatula (Klug, 1817)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 21.VII.1979, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Periclista lineolata (Klug, 1816)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 20.V.2002, from *Fraxinus ornus* L. (Oleaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Phymatocera aterrima (Klug, 1816)

Material examined – Hungary, Budaörs, 12.VI.1987, from *Polygonatum latifolium* (Jacq.) Druce (Asparagaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Rhadinoceraea reitteri Konow, 1890

Material examined – Hungary, Budapest, Békásmegyér, 12.IV.1977, from *Iris* sp. (Iridaceae), leg. A. Podlussány, det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Budapest, 18.V.2002, from *Iris* sp., leg. A. Podlussány, det. L. Zombori.

Tenthredinidae: Heterarthrinae*Caliroa annulipes* (Klug, 1816)

Material examined – Austria, Rappottenstein, ca. 23.VII.1987, from *Tilia cordata* Mill. (Malvaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Caliroa cerasi (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined – USSR Armenia [now Armenia], Sevan, 22.VI.1970, from *Cerasus vulgaris* Mill. (Rosaceae), and from *Prunus cerasifera* Ehrh. (Rosaceae), leg. Arutyunyan, det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Debrecen, 23.IX.1966, det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 29.VIII.1971, from *Cerasus vulgaris*, leg. & det. L. Zombori; same but 16.VIII.1973; same but 26.VIII.1973; Hungary, Tiszaigar, Arboretum, 19.IX.1977, from *Cerasus avium* Mönch. and from *Prunus* sp. (both Rosaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Zamárdi, 11.VIII.1981, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Remarks –The collector was not recorded for the material from Debrecen; according to Zoltán Varga (University of Debrecen, pers. comm.) the collector might be Zoltán Siroki (University of Debrecen).

Fenella arenariae Zombori, 1978

Material examined – Hungary, Budaörs, 16.IX.1977, from *Potentilla arenaria* Borkh. (Rosaceae), leg. J. Szócs, det. L. Zombori.

Fenusa pusilla (Lepeletier, 1823)

Material examined – Hungary, Siófok, from mine on *Betula pendula* Roth (Betulaceae), det. L. Zombori; Hungary, KNP [= Kiskunság National Park], Nagybugac, 18.VII.1979, from *Betula pendula*, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Remarks – Material from Siófok was found entirely desiccated and transferred into ethanol in 2025; the collector was not recorded.

Fenusella hortulana (Klug, 1818)

Material examined – Hungary, Farnos, 22.VII.1979, from mine on *Populus canadensis* Moench (Salicaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Heterarthrus aceris (Kaltenbach, 1856)

Material examined – Austria, Innsbruck, 2.VI.1974, from mine on *Acer pseudoplatanus* L. (Sapindaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Heterarthrus cuneifrons Altenhofer et Zombori, 1987

Material examined – Austria, Wien, ca. 6.VI.1976, leg. E. Altenhofer, det. E. Altenhofer & L. Zombori.

Heterarthrus flavicollis (Gussakovskij, 1947)

Material examined – USSR Armenia [now Armenia], Kirovakan, 15.VI.1966, from *Acer pseudoplatanus*, leg. Arutyunyan, det. L. Zombori.

Heterarthrus leucomelus (Klug, 1818)

Material examined – Austria, Linz, ca. 6.VIII.1976, from *Acer campestre* L. (Sapindaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer; Austria, Strasswalchen, 14.VII.1977, from *Acer campestre*, leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Remarks – Material from Linz was found entirely desiccated and transferred into ethanol in 2025.

Heterarthrus microcephalus (Klug, 1818)

Material examined – USSR Armenia [now Armenia], No. 101 [more precise collecting data not available], det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 18.VII.1976, from *Salix fragilis* L. (Salicaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori; same but 24.IX.1976; same but 16.X.1976; Hungary, Tiszaigar, Arboretum, 13.IX.1977, from *Salix alba* L. (Salicaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Heterarthrus nemoratus (Fallén, 1808)

Material examined – Austria, Mitterdorf, ca. 17.VIII.1976, from *Betula pubescens* Ehrh. (Betulaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer; Austria, Weitra, ca. 14.VIII.1978, from *Betula pendula*, leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Heterarthrus ochropoda (Klug, 1818)

Material examined – Hungary, Farnos, 4.VII.1973, from *Populus tremula* L. (Salicaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori; same but 22.VII.1973.

Heterarthrus vagans (Fallén, 1808)

Material examined – Austria, Styria, Wiel, 10.IX.1974, from *Alnus alnobetula* (Ehrh.) K. Koch (Betulaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer; Ukraine, Kárpátalja [= Zakarpattia Oblast], Máramarosi k. k. [= nature conservation area], Rahó [= Rahiv], 450 m, 12.VII.1996, from *Alnus incana* (L.) Mönch. (Betulaceae), leg. V. Ermolenko, det. L. Zombori.

Heterarthrus wuestneii (Konow, 1905)

Material examined – Austria, Linz, Asten, ca. 3.VI.1977, from *Acer campestre*, leg. & det. E. Altenhofer (as *Heterarthrus healyi* Altenhofer et Zombori, 1987); Austria, Wien, ca. 15.VI.1977, from *Acer pseudoplatanus*, leg. & det. E. Altenhofer (as *Heterarthrus aceris* (McLachlan, 1867)).

Remarks – Material from Linz was found entirely desiccated and transferred into ethanol in 2025.

Heterarthrus sp.

Material examined – Ukraine, Kárpátalja [= Zakarpattia Oblast], Máramarosi k. k. [= nature conservation area], Rahó [= Rahiv], 500 m, 12.VII.1996, from *Acer pseudoplatanus*, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Hinatara nigripes (Konow, 1907)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 20.V.1978, from *Acer campestre*, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Hinatara recta (Thomson, 1871)

Material examined – Austria, Linz, ca. 28.IV.1997, from *Acer platanoides* L. (Sapindaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Hinatara sp.

Material examined – Austria, Salzburg, ca. 23.V.1995, from *Acer pseudoplatanus*, leg. & det. E. Altenhofer; Switzerland, Delémont, ca. 6.VI.1976, from *Acer pseudoplatanus*, leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Remarks – Material from Switzerland was found entirely desiccated and transferred into ethanol in 2025.

Kaliofenusa ulmi (Sundeval, 1844)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagyharsány, 19.V.1976, from *Ulmus* sp. (Ulmaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 22.V.1973, from *Ulmus* sp., leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Metallus albipes (Cameron, 1875)

Material examined – Austria, Schweiggeners, ca. 11.IX.1977, from *Rubus idaeus* L. (Rosaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Metallus gei (Brischke, 1883)

Material examined – Austria, Inprugg, ca. 31. VIII. 1977, from *Geum urbanum* L. (Rosaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer; Austria, Neulengbach, ca. 19.IX.1977, from *Geum urbanum*, leg. & det. E. Altenhofer; Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 1.VII.1999, from *Geum urbanum*, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Metallus pumilus (Klug, 1816)

Material examined – Austria, Neulengbach, ca. 28.VI.1975, from *Rubus caesius* L. (Rosaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer; Hungary, Kunfehértó, Holdrutás forest, 23.VIII.1979, from *Rubus fruticosus* L. (Rosaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Kunszentmiklós, Koplaló, 24.VIII.1979, from *Rubus caesius* L., leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 3.IX.1975, from *Rubus* sp. (Rosaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori; same but 17.IX.1975, from *Rubus idaeus*; same but 30.IX.1975; Hungary, Nagyvisnyó, Nagyvölgy, 5.VII.1982, from *Rubus fruticosus*, leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Tihany, 3.VIII.1979, from *Rubus fruticosus*, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Metallus sp.

Material examined – Hungary, Újszentmargita, protected forest, 14.IX.1977, from *Rubus fruticosus*, leg. & det. L. Zombori; North Korea, Kangwon Province, Mt. Kumgangsan, 12.X.1978, from *Fragaria nipponica* Makino (Rosaceae), leg. A. Vojnits & L. Zombori (No. 489), det. L. Zombori.

Parna tenella (Klug, 1816)

Material examined – Austria, Linz, ca. 16.V.1976, from *Tilia cordata*, leg. & det. E. Altenhofer; same but ca. 28.IV.1977.

Profenusa pygmaea (Klug, 1816)

Material examined – Ukraine, Kárpátalja [= Zakarpattia Oblast], Máramarosi k. k. [= nature conservation area], Rahó [= Rahiv], 700–1200 m, 10.VII.1996, from *Quercus* sp. (Fagaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Profenusa sp.

Material examined – North Korea, Kangwon Province, Mt. Kumgangsan, 11.X.1978 [on the original label erroneously 1968], from *Quercus dentata* Thunb. (Fagaceae), leg. A. Vojnits & L. Zombori (No. 482), det. L. Zombori; same but 14.X.1978, from *Castanea* sp. (Fagaceae), (No. 501); North Korea, Kangwon Province, Samilpo Inlet, 13.X.1978, from *Quercus* sp., leg. A. Vojnits & L. Zombori (No. 492), det. L. Zombori.

Scolioneura betuleti (Klug, 1816)

Material examined – Austria, Langenschwand, ca. 9.VI.1977, from *Betula pendula*, leg. & det. E. Altenhofer; Austria, Mönichkirchen, ca. 22.IX.1975, from *Alnus alnobetula*, leg. E. Altenhofer, det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 4.VI.1977, *Betula pendula*, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Scolioneura tirolensis (Enslin, 1914)

Material examined – Switzerland, Gänsbrunnen, ca. 7.VI.1976, from *Salix caprea* L. (Salicaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Silliana lhommei (Hering, 1934)

Material examined – Yugoslavia, Istria [= either Croatia or Slovenia], ca. 8.IV.1977, from *Phillyrea* sp. (Oleaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Tenthredinidae: Tenthredininae
Macrophya albicincta (Schrank, 1776)

Material examined – Hungary, Budapest, Hűvösvölgy, 27.VI.1974, from *Sambucus ebulus* L. (Adoxaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Nagykovács, 4.VII.1976, from *Sambucus nigra* L. (Adoxaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Macrophya sp.

Material examined – USSR Georgia [now Georgia], Naa, Kodori Valley, 25.V.1975, from *Sambucus ebulus*, leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Alpár, Töserdő, 10.VI.1980, from *Sambucus nigra*, leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Szentmártonkáta, 1.VII.1976, from *Sambucus ebulus*, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Remarks – Material from Szentmártonkáta was found entirely desiccated and transferred into ethanol in 2025.

Tenthredopsis sp.

Material examined – Hungary, Újszentmargita, protected forest, 14.IX.1977, from *Calamagrostis epigejos* (L.) Roth (Poaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Tenthredinidae: Nematinae
Cladius pectinicornis (Geoffroy, 1785)

Material examined – Hungary, Fonyód, Fonyódliget, 5.VII.1986, from *Rosa canina* L. (Rosaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Craesus septentrionalis Linnaeus, 1758

Material examined – Austria, Pertholz, ca. 1.VIII.1979, from *Betula pendula*, leg. E. Altenhofer, det. L. Zombori.

Euura testaceipes (Brischke, 1883)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 5.X.1973, from gall on leaf vein of *Salix* sp. (Salicaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Euura venusta (Brischke, 1883)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 15.IX.1973, from gall on leaf stalk of *Salix fragilis* L. (Salicaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Euura sp.

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 30.VII.1976, from *Salix* sp., leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Hoplocampa brevis (Klug, 1816).

Material examined – Hungary, Debrecen, 7.V.1963, det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 7.V.1993, from *Pyrus communis* L. (Rosaceae), leg. B. Nagy, det. L. Zombori.

Remarks – The collector was not recorded for the material from Debrecen; according to Zoltán Varga (University of Debrecen, pers. comm.) the collector might be Zoltán Siroki (University of Debrecen).

Hoplocampa chrysorrhoea (Klug, 1816)

Material examined – Hungary, Budapest, 29.VI.1990, from *Ribes uva-crispa* L. (Rosaceae), leg. J. Pál, det. L. Zombori.

Hoplocampa crataegi (Klug, 1816)

Material examined – Hungary, Alpár, Töserdő, 10.VI.1980, from *Crataegus laevigata* (Poir.) DC. (Rosaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Hoplocampa minuta (Christ, 1791)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 24.V.1969, leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 20.V.1973, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Nematus pavidus (Audinet-Serville, 1823)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 16.IX.1975, from eggs on *Salix alba* var. *tristis*, leg. & det. L. Zombori; same but 19.IX.1975.

Hoplocampa pectoralis Thomson, 1871

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 30.V.1976, from *Crataegus* sp. (Rosaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Nematus trilineatus Norton, 1867

Material examined – Hungary, Újszentmargita, 3.VII.1974, from *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. (Fabaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Pontania proxima (Audinet-Serville, 1823)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 21.VII.1973, from *Salix* sp., leg. & det. L. Zombori (no preserved larvae since all specimens emerged on 27.VIII.1973, along with parasitic wasps); Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 15.IX.1973, from *Salix* sp., leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 4.IX.1976, from *Salix alba* var. *tristis*, leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 24.IX.1976, from *Salix fragilis*, leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Nagykovácsi, 9.X.1976, leg. & det. L. Zombori; Hungary, Tiszaigar, Arboretum, 13.IX.1977, from *Salix viminalis* L. (Salicaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Pontania vesicator (Bremsi-Wolf, 1849)

Material examined – Hungary, Tiszaigar, Arboretum, 13.IX.1977, from *Salix viminalis*, leg. & det. L. Zombori.; Slovakia, Rózsahegy [= Okres Ružomberok], Oszada [= Liptovská Osada], 25.VIII.1982, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Pontania viminalis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined – Hungary, Bugac, Ósborókás [= juniper forest], 11.VI.1980, from *Salix rosmarinifolia* L. (Salicaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Pontania sp.

Material examined – Ukraine, Kárpátalja [= Zakarpattia Oblast], Máramarosi k. k. [= nature conservation area], Rahó [= Rahiv], 800 m, 14.VII.1996, from *Salix triandra* L. (Salicaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Pristiphora pallipes Lepeletier, 1823

Material examined – Hungary, Debrecen, Pallag, 3.IX.1965, det. L. Zombori.

Remarks – The collector was not recorded; according to Zoltán Varga (University of Debrecen, pers. comm.) the collector might be Zoltán Siroki (University of Debrecen).

Pseudodineura enslini (Hering, 1923)

Material examined – Austria, Tauplitz, ca. 20.VI.1977, from *Trollius europaeus* L. (Ranunculaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Pseudodineura fuscula (Klug, 1816)

Material examined – Austria, Ritter camp, VI.1979, from *Ranunculus repens* L. (Ranunculaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Pseudodineura sp.

Material examined – Austria, Ritter camp, VI. 1979, from *Ranunculus platanifolius* L. (Ranunculaceae), leg. & det. E. Altenhofer.

Cephidæ*Cephus pygmaeus* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovács, 15.VIII.1974, from *Triticum aestivum* L. em. Fiori et Paol. (Poaceae), pupal case and prepupa, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Janus compressus (Fabricius, 1793)

Material examined – Hungary, Nagykovács, 1.VIII.1976, from *Pyrus* sp. (Rosaceae), leg. & det. L. Zombori; Romania, Erdély [= Transsylvania], Déva [= Deva], 1.VI.1993, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

Syrista parreyssii (Spinola, 1843)

Material examined – USSR Armenia [now Armenia], Yerevan, 1000 m, Bot. Garden [= botanical garden], 25.VII.1977, leg. & det. L. Zombori.

LIST OF UNIDENTIFIED MATERIAL

Armenia: Megradzor, 1600 m, 18.VII.1977, leg. L. Zombori, larvae from galls of *Salix* sp., three small larvae with yellow heads and white bodies. **Austria:** Kirchberg, 23.VII.1987, leg. E. Altenhofer, from *Quercus robur*, seven larvae with yellow heads and dirty yellow bodies. **Georgia:** Sukhumi, Gumista Valley, 19.V.1975, leg. L. Zombori, many larvae of different sizes; 27.V.1975, leg. L. Zombori, three large larvae, likely conspecific, with light yellowish heads and bodies, and abdomens with rows of dark dots on both sides. **Greece:** Marathon, 19.V.1977, leg. L. Zombori, a yellow-headed larva with robust body. **Hungary:** Abaliget, 29.VI.1978, leg. L. Zombori, from *Alnus* sp. (Betulaceae), one larva with yellow head and white body; same but from *Equisetum* sp., one larva with large, yellowish head and body; Budapest, Húvösvölgy, 15.VI.1976, leg. K. Sin, from *Quercus* sp. and *Ulmus* sp., three larvae (two light brown, one white), apparently representing two species; Bugac, Nagybugac, 18.VII.1979, leg. L. Zombori, larval skin from *Prunus* sp.; Csévharaszt, 22.VI.1977, leg. L. Zombori, fragments of a larva; same but several larvae with black heads and yellowish bodies; same but two larvae with yellowish heads and bodies; Darány, 20.VI.1978, leg. L. Zombori, from leaf of *Quercus* sp., one larva with yellowish head and bluish body; Eplény, Malomárok, 24.IX.1977, leg. L. Zombori, three larvae with yellow heads, their bodies with paired brownish lines; same but four larvae with light yellow heads, black eyes, and almost entirely white bodies; same but several larvae (in three

vials); same but several larvae with yellow heads, their bodies with paired brownish lines (in two vials); Fülöpháza, 5.IX.1978, leg. L. Zombori, three larvae, two with black, one with yellowish heads, bodies white, possibly representing two species; Hosszúhetény, 20.V.1976, leg. L. Zombori, two larvae with dark heads and bodies; Kerekegyháza, Kondor-tó [= Kondor lake], 23.VIII.1979, leg. L. Zombori, three larvae with yellowish heads, bodies with paired black dots; Kiskunság National Park, Bugac, Nagybugac, 18.VII.1978, leg. L. Zombori, from leaf of *Thelypteris palustris* Schott (Thelypteridaceae), one small larva with yellow head and body; Nagyiván, Kunmadaras, 30.VI.1976, leg. L. Zombori, one larva with light brown body; Nagykovácsi, 30.IX.1975, leg. L. Zombori, from *Rubus idaeus*, two larvae, their abdomens dorsally brownish; same but 29.VII.1979, from mine on *Syringa vulgaris* L. (Olaeaceae), larvae white, very slim, apparently with only 4–5 pairs of abdominal legs, thus are very unlikely sawfly larvae; same but 10.IX.1973, from *Rosa* sp., three larvae with black heads; same but 14.VIII.1973, swept, several larvae of apparently two species; same but 15.IX.1973, from *Salix* sp., parasitic wasp and a larval skin; same but 17.IX.1975, from *Rosa* sp., two larvae their bodies yellow with many small black dots; same but 17.VII.1981, from *Salix caprea*, two larvae, their heads black, bodies yellowish with four, longitudinally arranged dark dots; same but 21.VIII.1977, one larva with light brown head and white body; same but 23.IX.1975, swept from low vegetation in a mixed forest, three white larvae; same but 25.IX.1973, swept, two larvae, apparently representing two species; same but 26.V.1976, from *Betula* sp. (Betulaceae), one larva with brown head on both sides, body white; same but 28.VIII.1977, seven white larvae; same but 3.IX.1976, from leaf of *Populus canadensis*, six larvae with light brown heads and yellowish bodies; same but 30.IX.1975, from *Quercus* forest, three white larvae; same but 4.IX.1977, from *Betula* sp., two larvae with light brown heads and yellowish white bodies; same but 4.VII.1977, from mine in *Betula* sp., one light yellow larva; same but 5.VI.1977, from *Rosa* sp., larvae with light brown heads, and light yellow bodies with many short spines; same but 8.IX.1973, two large, yellowish white larvae, and one small, entirely white larva; same but 9.IX.1976, four larvae with yellow heads and white bodies; same but 23.VI.1974, from *Salix* sp., three larvae with black heads, their abdomens with rows of brown spots; Nagykovácsi, Kereszt-mező [= Kereszt field], 21.VI.1974, leg. L. Zombori, swept, three white larvae; Nagykovácsi, Nagyvölgy, 5.VII.1982, leg. L. Zombori, from *Corylus avellana* L. (Betulaceae), two larvae (one small, other one large, obviously representing two species; Nagyvisnyó, Feketevár-rét [= Feketevár meadow], 8.VII.1982, leg. L. Zombori, vial with a piece of *Pteridium aquilinum* leaf within, larva yellow, its head dark; Pécs, Tettye, 17.V.1976, leg. L. Zombori, one yellowish larva; Tahitótfalu, 26.IV.1989, leg. L. Zombori, from mine in *Quercus* sp., four larvae with yellowish heads and entirely white bodies; Tiszaigar, Arboretum, 13.IX.1977, leg. L. Zombori, from leaf of *Salix viminalis*, several larvae with black heads and yellow bodies, their abdomen on both sides with

three rows of black dots; Újszentmargita, 15.VI.1976, leg. L. Zombori, from *Quercus*, *Crataegus* and *Ulmus* spp., swept, several large- and small-bodied larvae, their colour white and light brown; same but 14.IX.1977, from *Humulus lupulus* L. (Cannabaceae), one larva with light brown head and body; same but several larvae with dark heads and bodies, their abdomen with five, longitudinally arranged dark spots, one larva very young, its body white and head black; Villányi Mts., Nagyharsány, 19.V.1976, leg. L. Zombori, one large, white larva; Vörs, 11.VI.1986, leg. L. Zombori, two larvae with yellow heads, their body greyish, both sides with longitudinal, light lines; Zamárdi, Töreki-láp [= Töreki bog], 11.VI.1986, leg. L. Zombori, twelve larvae with black heads, their bodies with paired, black dots. **North Korea:** Kangwon Province, Kumgangsán, 12 km from resthouse on road to Kwinyon-am, 14.V.1978, leg. A. Vojnits & L. Zombori (No. 502), one larva with yellow head and brownish body; Pyongyang City, 17.IX.1994, leg. F. Mészáros & L. Zombori, pupal cases and one yellowish white prepupa from twigs of *Rosa* sp.; South Pyongan Province, Lake Yonpung-ho, 10 km SW of Kaechon, 1.X.1978, leg. A. Vojnits & L. Zombori, from *Salix* cf. *fragilis*, three entirely white larvae and two prepupae. **Romania:** Transsylvania, Harghita County, Homoródfürdő [= Băile Homorod], 30.V.1990, leg. L. Zombori, larvae with partly brownish heads and white bodies; same but 20.V.1996, three slim, almost entirely white larvae; Transsylvania, Szeben [= Sibiu] County, Resinar [= Rășinari], 600 m, 12.VII.1997, leg. L. Zombori, from *Salix* sp., a very large larva (almost 40 mm long) with white head and light brown body; same but 12.VII.1997, from mine on *Betula* sp., two very slim, white larvae with yellowish heads; same but 1700 m, 15.VII.1997, many larvae with entirely white heads and bodies; Transsylvania, Bálványos [= Băile Bálványos, Turia], 2.VIII.2009, leg. L. Zombori, from *Salix caprea*, many larvae with brown heads and white bodies with longitudinally running rows of black dots, likely conspecific. **Slovakia:** Dobšiná Ice Cave, 1.VII.1981, leg. L. Zombori, from *Salix purpurea* L. (Salicaceae), many brown-headed larvae with white bodies. **Turkey:** 40 km W from Tekirdag, 24.V.1974, leg. L. Zombori, two large larvae, their heads marked with black dots, as are all abdominal segments on both sides. **Ukraine:** Kárpátalja [= Zakarpattia Oblast], Rahó [= Rahiv], along the river Tisza, 10.VII.1963, leg. V. Ermolenko, three larvae, apparently representing two species; Kárpátalja [= Zakarpattia Oblast], Máramarosi k. k. [= nature conservation area], Rahó [= Rahiv], 19.VI.1997, netted from *Pteridium aquilinum*, leg. L. Zombori, two larvae with light brown heads and bodies, apparently conspecific; Kárpátalja [= Zakarpattia Oblast], Máramarosi k. k. [= nature conservation area], Tiszabogdány [= Bohdan], Brebenyeszkul [= Brebeneskul], guest house, 600–700 m, 24.VII.1998, leg. L. Zombori, larvae with white heads and bodies, and black-headed specimens with yellowish body; Kanyaev, 18.VIII.2000, leg. L. Zombori, a large, yellowish white larva with two rows of large, black spots on each body segment, on bases of legs with small, black spots, body with long, stiff bristles, head with a large black spot.

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Acknowledgements – The author sincerely thanks the director general of the HNHM for giving the author the opportunity to borrow, study and identify the material treated in this paper, and the head of the Hymenoptera Collection of the HNHM, Zoltán Vas, for organising the administration and transportation of the loan. The author is grateful to Zoltán Barina (WWF Hungary) for his corrections regarding botanical names, and to the editorial board for their improvements on the manuscript. Special appreciation is due to all collectors who donated larval specimens, first and foremost to Ewald Altenhofer, Attila Podlussány, János Pál, Valeriy Mikhailovich Ermolenko, Arutyunyan, Zoltán Siroki, and Katalin Sin. Thanks are due to Győző Szél (HNHM) for checking several locality names in the Caucasus and the Far East.

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